

CAAT: Consistency as a Theory (Artifact)

Thomas Haas Roland Meyer Hernan Ponce de Leon

Abstract

This document explains how to reproduce the results from Section 7 of the paper *CAAT: Consistency as a Theory* published at OOPSLA 2022.

1 Getting Started

The file `caat-oopsla-2022` contains a docker image with an Ubuntu system. The system has the following tools installed: HERD, DARTAGNAN, GENMC and NIDHUGG. To load the docker image, run

```
$ docker load < caat-oopsla-2022
```

The docker image contains all tools for the evaluation. To run the docker image, run

```
$ docker run -it caat-oopsla-2022 /bin/bash
```

2 Step-by-Step Guide

First, load the docker image as described in the Getting Started section. We provide scripts (`/home/Dat3M/scripts`) that run the tools over our set of benchmarks and generate the verification data. To generate all the data, run the scripts

```
$ cd /home/Dat3M  
$ bash scripts/litmus.sh  
$ bash scripts/oopsla.sh
```

This will produce `.csv` files that contain the verification times of all tools. The first script is expected to finish after one hour. The second one takes close to 15 hs. Once all data have been generated, to generate figures of the verification times similar to those in the paper simply run the python script `plot.py`

```
$ cd /home/Dat3M
$ python3 scripts/plot.py
```

The output files will be generated in the folder `Dat3M/output/Figures/`. The figures can be copied to the local host by running

```
$ docker cp <containerId>:/path/container /host/path/target
```

Resource Limits. To guarantee that the evaluation uses reasonable resources, we set time and memory limits to the verification runs. For each litmus test, we set a 10s timeout and no memory limit. Litmus tests are minimal and usually don't require much resources. For each of the benchmarks in Fig. 8, we set a 15m timeout and 4GB of memory for the JVM (using option `-Xmx4g` when running DARTAGNAN and CAAT). These benchmarks do not impose memory problems for GENMC and NIDHUGG and thus we impose no limit for those tools.

When a resource limit is hit (time or memory), an error is output and the instance is counted as taking the full timeout time in the statistics. In the case of litmus tests, HERD is expected to hit the timeout in 1% of the instances, which does not influence the overall generated statistics. We have also observed that the eager encoding of DARTAGNAN can produce an out-of-memory error. This only happens on one of the large benchmarks where the eager encoding of DARTAGNAN becomes too large.

Console Output. The HERD tool reaches the time limit for 1% of the tests. Because of this, the console output will contain several entries such as

```
[ERROR] HerdAARCH64>AbstractExternalTool ... TestTimedOut
[ERROR] HerdLinux>AbstractExternalTool ... TestTimedOut
```

The eager encoding of DARTAGNAN reaches the Java heap space limit we set for one of the large benchmarks, so the console output contains

```
Exception in thread "main" java.lang.OutOfMemoryError: Java heap space
```

The console output also contains warnings

```
WARNING: Non-sequentially consistent CMPXCHG instruction interpreted  
as sequentially consistent.  
WARNING: Atomic xchg support is experimental under dependency-tracking  
models!
```

These are either created by NIDHUGG or GENMC. They do not affect the statistics and can be safely ignored.